

WOMEN IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY WHAT DOES THE LITERATURE SAY?

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Annotation: *Skill gaps are a key constraint to innovation, hindering productivity growth and economic development. In particular, shortages in the supply of trained professionals in disciplines related to Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) may weaken the innovation potential of a society. A wide gender gap has persisted over the years at all levels of STEM disciplines throughout the world. Although the participation of women in higher education has increased, they are still underrepresented. Latin America is no exception. The untapped potential of fully trained and credentialed women represents an important lost opportunity not only for women themselves but also for society as a whole. Although there is growing recognition of the importance of the issue in developing countries, Latin America faces a lack of information that prevents researchers from deepening the understanding of this phenomenon and policymakers from designing effective interventions.*

Key words: *women, technology, innovation, development, higher education, scientific, academic.*

Skill gaps are a key constraint to innovation, hindering productivity growth and economic development. In particular, shortages in the supply of trained professionals in disciplines related to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) may weaken the innovation potential of a society. Empirical studies show that countries with a higher proportion of engineering graduates tend to grow faster than countries with a higher proportion of graduates in other disciplines (Murphy, Schleifer, and Vishny, 1991). In addition, future technical change is likely to be linked to abilities and tasks related to STEM disciplines.¹ A wide gender gap has persisted over the years at all levels of STEM disciplines throughout the world. Although women have made important advances in their participation in higher education, they are still underrepresented in these fields. This problem is more acute at the senior-most levels of academic and professional hierarchies.² Latin America is no exception. Although 60 percent of tertiary graduates and 45 percent of researchers in Latin America are women (UNESCO, 2007) - surpassing all other regions, including Europe (33.9 percent), Oceania (39.2 percent), and Asia

(18 percent) - in STEM disciplines this percentage drops to 36 percent. Only 11 percent of Latin American female graduates of tertiary education are in STEM fields, while STEM fields represent 12.3 percent of new enrollments at the tertiary level (UNESCO UIS database). Moreover, participation of Latin American women at the higher strata of research is rare. For example, while in Brazil 49 percent of researchers are female, only 27 percent of women lead research groups, compared to 32 percent for men (CNPq database, 2012). Gender equality in science, technology, and innovation is not simply a matter of fairness. A more equitable gender balance is believed to enhance the recruitment of the most talented, irrespective of gender (European Commission, 2008a), tapping a partially unexploited resource.

A more inclusive workforce is assumed to be more innovative and productive than one which is less so (National Academy of Sciences, 2006). Having scientists and engineers with diverse backgrounds, interests, and cultures assures better scientific and technological results and the best use of those results (Lane, 1999). Gender equality is seen as a way to promote scientific and technological excellence rather than just improving opportunities for women (genSET, 2011).

Barriers to the Participation of Women in STEM A full understanding of the factors constraining women's career paths in STEM has often been hampered by the persistence of several myths and clichés. Table 1 presents some of these commonly held beliefs and contrasts them with existing evidence. The various factors that have been identified in the economic literature at different stages of the career pipeline are then presented (Figure 1). These include: (i) higher education; (ii) stage of career development; and 4 (iii) scientific productivity. Although some factors specifically affect a particular career stage, several of them are present throughout the career path. Table 1. Myths about Women in STEM and Evidence Refuting Them

Myth	Evidence
Women don't have ability and drive to succeed in STEM.	Studies of brain structure and function, hormonal modulation, human cognitive development, and human evolution have not found any significant biological difference in men's and women's ability to perform in science and mathematics (Ceci and Williams, 2007). In the United States, female performance in high school mathematics matches that of males (NAS, 2007). Among adolescents in the top 1 percent of mathematics ability, boys are almost twice more likely than girls to obtain degrees in physical sciences and engineering (Weinberger, 2005). Lack of innate mathematics ability could not explain this difference. The underrepresentation problem in science faculties will be naturally solved with the passing of time. In the United States, women's

underrepresentation along the academic career is present also in fields that have had a large proportion of female Ph.Ds. for 30 years (NAS, 2007). Academia is a meritocracy. Although scientists like to believe that they “choose the best” based on objective criteria, decisions are influenced by factors—including biases about race, sex, geographic location of a university, and age—that have nothing to do with the quality of the person or work being evaluated. An article receives less favorable reviews when it is identified as written by a female author (Paludi and Bauer, 1983). Changing the rules of selection and promotion to foster gender equality means that the standards of excellence and advancement will be adversely affected. Throughout a scientific career, advancement depends upon judgments about one’s performance by more senior scientists and engineers. This process does not optimally select and advance the best scientists and engineers, because of implicit bias and disproportionate weighting of qualities that are stereotypically male. Reducing these sources of bias will foster excellence in science and engineering fields. Wenneras and Wold (1997) state that “a woman has to be more than twice as productive as a man to be judged equally competent.” 5 Female faculty members are less productive than their male counterparts. The publication productivity of women science and engineering faculty has increased over the last 30 years and is now comparable to men’s. The critical factor affecting publication productivity is access to institutional resources; marriage, children, and elder care responsibilities have minimal effects. According to Sedeño (ed.) (2001), “women are members of low power committees, have fewer financial resources, less support from staff, or are located in offices which are further away, lack access to “beginners’ networks” in order to obtain information, and do not have models or mentors to ask for advice or support.” Symonds (2007) finds that funding still depends on the number of papers published, which keeps men at the top. Women are not as competitive as men. Women don’t want jobs in academia. Similar proportions of men and women science and engineering doctoral students plan to enter postdoctoral study or academic employment. Women are more interested in family than in careers. Many women scientists and engineers persist in their pursuit of academic careers despite severe conflicts between their roles as parents and as scientists and engineers. These efforts, however, are often not recognized as representing the high level of dedication to their careers they actually represent. Women take more time off due to childrearing, so they are a bad investment. On average, women take more time off during their early careers to meet their caregiving responsibilities. But, by middle age, a man is likely to

take more sick leave than a woman. The system as it currently exists has worked well in producing great science; why change it? Career impediments based on gender or racial or ethnic bias deprive the nation of talented and accomplished researchers. Source: Extracted and adapted from NAS (2007). Higher Education Although the first interaction with science and mathematics occurs in elementary and secondary education, tertiary education is the critical step in which students decide their future careers. ³ The transition from high school to higher education has been identified as the point at which both the largest proportion of students leave the science and technology trajectory and the exit rates of women exceed those of men by the largest margin (Xie and Shauman, 2003). At the same time, women seem less inclined than men to choose a STEM discipline when completing a nonscientific or technological track in high school. While women's participation overall in higher education has been growing around the world in the past decades, tertiary enrollment rate increases have been concentrated in fields where women's participation was already high (UNESCO, 2007).

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